

A meal detection approach based on parity space to detect untreated meals in subjects with Type 1 diabetes*

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Abstract—In this paper a data-driven fault detection technique based on parity space is applied to the problem of detecting unannounced meals for type 1 diabetes patients. This method involves the generation and evaluation of a residual signal to detect faults (unannounced meals) acting on the system (patient). Insulin on Board (IOB), meal intake, glucose and its second derivative have been selected as input signals to generate the residuals, and the parity space matrices are estimated using 8-hour training in silico data generated by the UVA/Padova simulator. The residual evaluation module compares the residual with a threshold that is optimized for each patient using 2-day tuning data. The complete system is evaluated on 1-week scenario obtaining promising results (TPR=95%, PPV=72%) with a detection delay of 42 minutes for 80% of patients. For the 20 outlier patients, a fine-tuning and patient-tailored input signal processing are proposed as a future development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Type 1 diabetes (T1D) is an autoimmune disease involving the destruction of pancreatic β -cells responsible for insulin release, the hormone fundamental to regulate Blood Glucose level (BG). Being not able to regulate their BGs, people with T1D experience prolonged periods in the so-called hyperglycemia (BG > 180 mg/dl), which leads to cardiovascular diseases. In order to avoid them, exogenous insulin injections are required to keep BG in a safe range of 70–180 mg/dl. On the other side, excessive insulin dosages would bring BGs below these limits (the so-called hypoglycemia) leading to diabetic coma and even death. For this reason,

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insulin injection has to be carefully dosed, in particular in the postprandial periods to balance out the effects of the meals on BGs. A deficiency of insulin in the postprandial period will result in hyperglycemia, while an overdose will result in hypoglycemia. One of the most successful and established therapies is the Basal-Bolus Therapy (BBT) in which the insulin injection is considered as the sum of two separate signals: the basal, a piecewise constant amount delivered during fasting periods dependent from the circadian cycle that tackles glycemia variations through the day, and the bolus, injected only in the postprandial period to compensate the meal effects and has to be tailored considering the carbohydrates intake. This therapy has the downside, apart from some optional safety measures, to be completely open loop since no Continuous Glycemia Monitoring (CGM) sensor is needed. In the last decades, with the availability of the CGM sensors and insulin pumps, a new system called Artificial Pancreas (AP) has been developed: it consists in a control algorithm which manages the insulin injection and directly command the pump, exploiting the glucose measure coming from the CGM sensor. The AP can be categorized as a Hybrid Closed-Loop (HCL) control if it requires meal announcements and carbohydrates estimation by the patient to calculate the meal bolus; it is a Fully Closed Loop system (FCL) if the control algorithm is in charge of managing the meal without any information about its time and carbohydrate intake. The FCL introduces delays connected to the digestion and to the subcutaneous nature of the CGM, while the HCL requires the patient to announce and estimate meal sizes. If in HCL control the meal is not announced, no insulin bolus would be injected, resulting in a hyperglycemia. It is fundamental to detect unannounced meals in HCL, to alert the patient and take mitigation actions. Various alarm systems have been developed and presented in literature for these purposes exploiting different kind of approaches. For example, Dassau et al. [1] proposes a majority voting system, for which each voter verifies the excess of a threshold for a specific parameter: the ROC computed directly from the signal of the CGM sensor, the BG estimation via a Kalman filter, the first and second derivative of the estimated BG. Samadi et al. [2] and [3] similarly propose a calculation of the first and second derivative of a filtered CGM signal and finally detect meals with a threshold based on those parameters. Ramkissoon et al. [4] estimates system states through an Unscented Kalman filter (UKF) having as inputs glucose and insulin infusion rate, exploiting state estimation for the forward difference of the disturbance parameter and the glucose value from a CGM sensor, it is possible to apply

a threshold to this covariance to detect unannounced meals. Cameron et al. [5] uses a model to predict future CGM, exploiting actual glucose and insulin readings, and a meal is detected when the difference between prediction and CGM exceeds a threshold. Using multiple simulations of different sizes, time and carbs intake of the unannounced meals can be also estimated. Xie et al.[6] used a Variable State Dimension (VSD) approach, developed to detect unknown inputs in the system. This approach implies a model of the system where no disturbance is present called quiescent model. An Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) estimates and predicts the states, and a disturbance is detected when the value from a fading memory average of innovations exceeds a threshold. Daniels et al. [7] use a seq2seq model to classify the meal presence: both the encoder and decoder are based on Long-Short Term Memory networks. With this approach, the estimated quantiles of a 20 minutes glucose trajectory are generated: then, a meal is detected if a significant and persistent deviation in the measured glucose trajectory from the estimated one arises.

As an alternative interpretation with respect to the aforementioned literature, the meal detection can be considered as a Fault Detection (FD) problem, where the fault is the carbohydrate intake without a proper insulin treatment to compensate its effect on the glucose. During the past two decades, model based FD techniques for linear time invariant (LTI) systems have been well established and a large number of standard methods are available for the FD system design, if a model of the system is available [8], [9]. In the AP context, a specialized model for each patient is rarely available, and the average one is characterized by huge uncertainties. However, residual generation schemes can be realized directly using test data from each patient, without an a-priori model, applying data-driven design techniques [10] that open the possibility of a personalized meal detection algorithm. The main idea of data-driven residual generator techniques is to identify a primary form of residual generators directly from test data and then to create a FD system based on it. In this work, the methodology reported in [10] is extended to design a meal detection tool based on a residual generator to be integrated in a HCL AP. The paper is organised as follows: Section II describes the Data-Driven Fault Detection (DDFD) technique and how it is adapted for the unannounced meal detection problem; Section III describes the simulation protocol and the tuning of the proposed module; results and future developments are discussed in Section IV. Finally, the conclusions are reported in Section V.

II. METHODS

In this Section, the Data-Driven Fault Detection (DDFD) approach is described and its adaptation to perform the detection of the meal in the AP context is introduced. The fault detection approach consists of two major parts (see Fig. 1): *residual generation* and *residual evaluation*. The goal of a residual generator is to generate a *residual signal* $r(k)$ that presents the key feature of having high values when a fault is present, while low values (ideally zero) in absence of faults.

Fig. 1: DDFD approach scheme.

The goal of the residual evaluator is to define the presence of faults comparing $r(k)$ with a properly tuned threshold t_h . In the following, the procedure to generate the residual and to tune its threshold are described in details.

A. Data-driven residual generation

Consider the discrete-time LTI system described as

$$\begin{cases} x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k) + B_f f(k) \\ y(k+1) = Cx(k) + Du(k) + D_f f(k) \end{cases},$$

where $x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, $u(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m_u \times 1}$, $y(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times 1}$, $f(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m_f \times 1}$ denotes the vectors of state variables, system inputs, outputs and faults acting on the system, respectively. Assuming that the system is not subject to faults ($f(k) = 0, \forall k$), the vector of the outputs $Y_s(k)$, from time $k-s$ to k , can be written according to the *parity relation*

$$Y_s(k) = H_{0,s}x(k-s) + H_{u,s}U_s(k), \quad (1)$$

where

$$Y_s(k) = \begin{bmatrix} y(k-s) \\ y(k-s+1) \\ \vdots \\ y(k) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(s+1)p \times 1}$$

$$U_s(k) = \begin{bmatrix} u(k-s) \\ u(k-s+1) \\ \vdots \\ u(k) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(s+1)m_u \times 1}$$

with

$$H_{0,s} = \begin{bmatrix} C \\ CA \\ \vdots \\ CA^s \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(s+1)p \times n}$$

$$H_{u,s} = \begin{bmatrix} D & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ CB & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ CA^{s-1}B & \cdots & CB & D \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(s+1)p \times m_u}$$

The matrices A, B, B_f, C, D and D_f , as well as the state vector $x(k-s)$, are generally unknown; instead, the vectors

Y_s and U_s can be measured and stored for the required time steps. The residual signal is defined as [10]:

$$r(k) = v_s^T \cdot (Y_s(k) - H_{u,s} U_s(k)), \quad (2)$$

where $v_s \in \mathbb{R}^{(p(s+1)) \times 1}$, $v_s \neq 0$ is the *parity vector* which satisfies $v_s^T \cdot H_{0,s} = 0$ and the set $H_{0,s}^\perp = \{v_s^T | v_s^T H_{0,s} = 0\}$ is called *parity space*.

In order to design the residual generator block, the vectors v_s^T and $v_s^T H_{u,s}$ have to be identified. In DDFD approaches, this is achieved by splitting the input and output vectors in past and future components, $\mathbf{U}_p, \mathbf{U}_f$ and $\mathbf{Y}_p, \mathbf{Y}_f$, called Hankel matrices and defined as follows

$$\mathbf{U}_p = \begin{bmatrix} U(i - s_p) \\ \vdots \\ U(i - 1) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{U}_f = \begin{bmatrix} U(i) \\ \vdots \\ U(i + s_f - 1) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_p = \begin{bmatrix} Y(i - s_p) \\ \vdots \\ Y(i - 1) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Y}_f = \begin{bmatrix} Y(i) \\ \vdots \\ Y(i + s_f - 1) \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$U(j) = [u(j) \quad \dots \quad u(j + N - 1)], \quad j \geq 0$$

$$Y(j) = [y(j) \quad \dots \quad y(j + N - 1)], \quad j \geq 0$$

and, considering that in this new notation $s = s_f - 1$, the residual can be rewritten as

$$r(k) = v_{s_f-1}^T \cdot (Y_{s_f-1}(k) - H_{u,s_f-1} U_s(k)), \quad (3)$$

where s_p and s_f are the past and future horizon ($s_p, s_f \geq n$ and $s_p, s_f \in \mathbb{Z}$) while N is the number of samples considered to estimate $v_{s_f-1}^T$ and $v_{s_f-1}^T H_{u,s_f-1}$.

Define the augmented data matrices Z_p, Z_f and the instrumental variable \mathcal{I} as

$$Z_p = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}_p \\ \mathbf{U}_p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(s_p p + s_p m_u) \times N},$$

$$Z_f = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}_f \\ \mathbf{U}_f \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(s_f p + s_f m_u) \times N},$$

$$\mathcal{I} = \frac{1}{N} Z_f Z_p.$$

By performing a singular value decomposition so that

$$\mathcal{I} = U_Z \Sigma_Z V_Z^T = \begin{bmatrix} U_{Z,11} & U_{Z,12} \\ U_{Z,21} & U_{Z,22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{Z,1} & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_{Z,2} \end{bmatrix} V_Z^T,$$

with

$$\Sigma_{Z,2} = 0 \in \mathbb{R}^{(s_f p - n) \times (p s_p + m_u s_p - m_u s_f - n)},$$

the parity space H_{0,s_f-1}^\perp can be obtained together with the parity vector $v_{s_f-1}^T$ as [10]:

$$H_{0,s_f-1}^\perp = U_{Z,12}^T, \quad H_{0,s_f-1}^\perp H_{s_f-1,u} = -U_{Z,22}^T$$

$$v_{s_f-1}^T \in H_{0,s_f-1}^\perp, \quad v_{s_f-1}^T H_{u,s_f-1} \in H_{0,s_f-1}^\perp H_{u,s_f-1}$$

which allow to compute the residuals as reported in (3).

B. Data-driven residual generation for meal detection

The application of data-driven fault detection techniques has been successfully applied in several industrial applications [11]. However, to our knowledge, this is the first time this methodology has been applied to the problem of detecting unannounced meals. The system under study is the patient with insulin injection, $i(k)$ as inputs and glucose measure, $G(k)$, as output; additional information available for the residual generator consists of the announced carbohydrates intake, $m(k)$.

Considering the high non linearity of the system, the time-variability and the huge uncertainties, the selection of the inputs of the residual generator is not trivial. They have to be informative enough to allow the detection of unexpected event (i.e. unannounced meals) without being affected by other possible disturbances. In the context of meal detection, informative signals revealed to be the Insulin On Board, $IOB(k)$ [7], and the second derivative of the glycemia, $\ddot{G}(k)$, computed with backward difference [1], [2], [3]. The IOB [12] represents the insulin injected in the past that is still active at the current time. It is a weighted integral of the insulin, being more informative with respect to the insulin since the latter represents an instantaneous value just injected, while the IOB contains the history of the treatment. For the proposed meal detection tool, the inputs of the residual generator are $u(k) = [IOB(k) \quad m(k)]$, while the outputs are $y(k) = [G(k) \quad \ddot{G}(k)]$. The parameters to be designed are: the number of underlying states of the system (n), the past and future horizons (s_p, s_f) and the length of the training period (N). The number of states n defines which part of the matrix U_Z is used to create the parity space matrix H_{0,s_f-1}^\perp ; since a data-driven approach is used in this work, n is not known and has to be defined considering that there is an upper bound ($s_p, s_f \geq n$) and not an explicit lower bound, although n needs to be high enough to represent sufficiently well the patient glycemia evolution. The parameter n can be properly estimated looking at the magnitude of the singular values of the matrix Σ_Z . The horizons s_p and s_f are related to the length of data used to compute the residual and to the time constants of the system [10]. The selection of N defines the period used to estimate the parity matrices. Selecting periods of time in which multiple inputs occur simultaneously should be avoided in order to clearly highlight the behaviour of interest. Since the desired residual should present high values when a fault is present, while low values (ideally zero) in absence of the unannounced meals, it is important to consider not only the magnitude of the residual but also its sign.

C. Residual evaluation

The residual signal has to be evaluated by a decision block that compares its value with respect to a threshold tuned for each patient. If the residual is higher for a significant amount of time (N_s samples) then the alarm of unannounced meal is raised.

In fault detection it is important to notify faults promptly, and in the case of unannounced meals this becomes even

more crucial: if the patient is alerted too late with respect to the meal time t_m , a mitigation action (such as a correction bolus) could result into hypoglycemia. For this reason it is necessary to tune an optimal threshold value t_h^* for each patient i : the alarm system tuned with different values of t_h will be evaluated in terms of False Positive (FP , the number of times the alarm is triggered without the presence of an unannounced meal) and False Negative (FN , the number of unannounced meals that are not detected) in order to select the one that minimize these quantities.

In addition, the detection delay (dd) is also considered in the optimization problem. It is important that dd is lower than a time threshold δ_{det} in order to avoid wrong mitigation actions due to late alarms. If an alarm is raised in the Detection Window $DW = [t_m, t_m + \delta_{det}]$, it will be considered a True Positive (TP), while if it falls in the Window $W = [t_m + \delta_{det}, t_m(j+1)]$ it is considered a FP since it is raised too far from the event. If no alarm is present in the DW , a FN is generated. Following these considerations, an optimization problem that minimizes the cost function $\mathcal{J}(t_h)$ is designed for each patient exploiting his/her own data taking into account the performance of the meal detection system:

$$\begin{aligned} t_h^* &= \min_{t_h} \mathcal{J}(t_h) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & t_h \geq 0 \\ & t_h \leq t_h^{max} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where the upper bound t_h^{max} is a parameter to be tuned and the cost function is defined as follows

$$\mathcal{J}(t_h) = \sum_j FP_j(t_h) + \sum_\nu FN_\nu(t_h) + \sum_\nu ddn_\nu(t_h),$$

where $j = 1, \dots, N_m$ is an index associated with every meal, N_m is the number of meals in the selected period, $\nu = 1, \dots, N_\nu$ is an index associated with every unannounced meal, N_ν is the number of unannounced meals in the selected period, FP_l and FN_l are the metrics related to the l^{th} meal and ddn_ν is the normalized value of dd with respect to the postprandial period $[t_m, t_m + \delta_{det}]$ of the ν^{th} meal.

As stated before, the sign of the residual holds valuable information, but can not be determined a priori and it is unique to each patient. In order to take into account this aspect, the optimization problem (4) is repeated twice, once with the original residual ($r(k)$) and other with its opposite ($-r(k)$). Two optimal thresholds (t_{h+}^*, t_{h-}^*) are obtained and the optimal t_h^* is the one associated with the best cost; the optimal sign (s_r) is also recorded for each specific patient. In order to take into account the presence of announced meals whose dynamic is different from the one used to estimate the for parity space, the alarm system is turned off for δ_{undet} [min] after the announcements. It is in line with the purpose of the system to detect only unannounced meals.

III. SIMULATIONS

A. The UVA/Padova simulator

The proposed work has been developed by using the UVA/Padova simulator, a metabolic simulator approved by

the Food and Drugs Administration (FDA) as substitute of animal test. It is a software available commercially and largely used in literature [13], but also to design and test the AP control strategies as well as safety modules [14], [15], [16], [17] tested in clinical trials. It includes a compartmental model equipped with a population of 300 patients (100 children, 100 adolescents and 100 adults) that are able to represent the metabolic behaviour of the entire diabetic population. The proposed meal detection tool has been designed and tested using the 100 in silico adult patients provided by this FDA-accepted simulator.

B. Scenario

In order to generalise the results, the tuning of the residual generator is performed using data of an untreated lunch, while the tuning of the residual evaluator and the test of alarm system are performed using unannounced breakfast and announced lunch/dinner. A meal scenario comprising of 10 days has been simulated on the entire population under the BBT: the first day (day-1) is designed to estimate $v_{s_f-1}^\top$ and $v_{s_f-1}^\top H_{s_f-1,u}$ (training dataset), containing an untreated lunch; day-2 and day-3 are used to optimise t_h and the residual sign (tuning dataset); lastly, the remaining week is used for testing the performances of the system (testing dataset). For this reason, day-1 involves only one lunch at 13:00 of 20g while day-2 and day-3 implement a realistic scenario during which the patient follows a precise diet with breakfast at 7:30 of 40g, lunch at 13:00 of 50g and dinner at 20:00 of 70g. The last part of the simulation includes one week during which the patient follows a protocol similar to the one observed during day-2 and day-3, in which meals are taken at the same time as day-2-3 while including reasonable uncertainties on the carbohydrate content ($\pm 30\%$) drawn from a uniform distribution. The details of the carbohydrate content are reported in Table I.

C. Parameters settings

The design of the alarm system has been carried on following a trial and error approach to maximize the performances on the tuning dataset, after which the best settings resulted $n = 8$, $s_p = s_f = 24$, $N = 96$, $t_h^{max} = 10$, $\delta_{det} = 120$ [min] and $\delta_{undet} = 180$ [min]. Given the CGM sample time of 5 [min], the past horizon results to be equal to 2 hours, while the period to estimate the parity space matrices lasts 8 hours. In particular, this training period ranges from 8:00 to 16:00 of day-1: it includes the first 4 hours during which the relation between basal insulin and glycemia is well represented and the the last 4 hours where the BG rise due to meal intake is present.

D. Performance metrics

The performance of the method is evaluated through the following metrics:

- True Positive Rate (TPR), or sensitivity, to measure the proportion of positives that are correctly identified

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

	mealtime	training	tuning			testing					
		day-1	day-2	day-3	day-4	day-5	day-6	day-7	day-8	day-9	day-10
breakfast	7:30	-	40	40	49	36	48	29	31	42	41
lunch	13:00	20	50	50	62	45	60	36	38	53	51
dinner	20:00	-	70	70	87	63	83	51	54	74	71

TABLE I: Meal sizes [g] used in simulation

Fig. 2: Performance indexes boxplot of the population using testing dataset.

- Positive Predictive Value (PPV), or precision, to measure the proportion of positives that are correctly identified over all the positive or negative predictions

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

- F1 score (F1) to measure the harmonic average of the precision and sensitivity, F1 score reaches its best value at 1 (perfect precision and sensitivity) and worst at 0

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot TPR \cdot PPV}{TPR + PPV} \quad (7)$$

For each index, the mean (\pm standard deviation, SD) for normally distributed data or the median [25th-75th percentiles] for the non-Gaussian case has been computed over the patient cohort as cumulative index of the entire population.

IV. RESULTS

The results of the alarm system are summarized in Table II in terms of TPR, PPV, and F1 obtained during the 7 days of the testing dataset by the entire population (first row). The testing dataset contains 7 unannounced breakfasts that have been successfully detected in the 92% of the cases; the alarm is correctly activated in the 68% of the cases, showing limited false alarms. Table II also reports the detection delay dd , it is worth to note that the meals are detected on average within 63 [min] after the meal, a time sufficient to allow an action to mitigate hyperglycemia.

The distributions of these metrics are represented in Fig. 2 for the entire population of the UVA/Padova simulator. Analyzing these graphs, it is clear that the proposed method is reliable in detecting unannounced meals for the entire population ($TPR > 71\%$); on the other hand, even if the

Fig. 3: Boxplot for the distribution of the cost $\mathcal{J}(t_h^*)$ computed on the tuning dataset of the whole population.

mean PPV is acceptable (68%), some patients present poor performance. From a deeper analysis these critical patients resulted to be 20 outliers of the $\mathcal{J}(t_h^*)$ distribution computed on the tuning dataset as shown in Fig. 3 and referred in the following as the critical subgroup (c-subgroup).

For this reason, an additional analysis excluding these critical patients has been performed as reported in Table II (second row). It can be noticed that on this well-performing subgroup of 80 patients (w-subgroup) the TPR reaches 95% with a PPV of 72%, also the delay obtains an improvement decreasing to 42 [min]. This detection delay is short enough to allow a prompt reaction of the controller in an AP and this system could be tested in silico in conjunction with any insulin delivery system (HCL/FCL AP or BBT). Fig. 5 reports the results obtained in one day of the testing dataset for a case-study patient. The glucose profile detected by the sensor and the meal intake are reported on the top. The unannounced breakfast causes persistent hyperglycemia until the lunch even if the carbohydrate intake is limited. On the contrary, the dinner is well controlled. The residual signal, r (on the bottom) presents high values in correspondence of the unannounced meal, while it assumes negative values if the meal is associated with an insulin bolus. This behaviour allows the system to correctly detect only the unannounced meal. Note that at the end of W , the system arises a FP , but the glucose level is particularly high in that period: a mitigation action will not cause hypoglycemia, if properly sized. Then, the mean BG measured in correspondence of the FPs is analyzed for the w-subgroup (Fig. 4): when FPs occur, the patients' mean BG exceeds 140 mg/dl for the 75% of the subjects. A reasonable mitigation action should not lead to dangerous hypoglycemia even if a meal is wrongly detected. This assumption has to be test through extensively simulations with different scenarios on the w-subgroup. For the patients belonging to c-subgroup, a fine-tuning of the residual generator could improve their performance: for example, the input and output signals of the residual generator could be tailored to the specific subject, considering other information such as the Carbohydrates On Board (COB, [18]) and the

Fig. 4: Boxplot for the distribution of the mean BG of the 80 well performing patients measured in correspondence of FPs in the testing dataset.

Fig. 5: Profile of the glucose and the residual obtained for a case-study patient of the w-subgroup for one day of the testing dataset: glucose profile and meal distribution (top), residual and threshold (bottom). DW is highlighted in green, W s are reported in orange. TP are marked with green square, FP with red diamond and FN with red square.

ROC. Moreover, considering the unique settings used for the entire population, a patient-tailored tuning could be required for these critical subjects. The high inter-patient variability makes this procedure not trivial and it is proposed as a future development of this work.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper a DDFD method is proposed to detect unannounced meals for patients with T1D. This method has been tuned and tested using the commercially available UVA/Padova simulator on 100 in silico adult patients. For 80% of the patients the detection of the unannounced meals present satisfying performances with a TPR of 95.2% and a PPV of 71.8%. The FPs of these patients are mainly associated with hyperglycemia events suggesting that a mitigation action triggered by them should not lead to hypoglycemia. The remaining 20 critical patients present poor performance in terms of PPV requiring a deeper analysis, e.g. to propose

# patients	TPR	PPV	F1	dd
100	91.8 ± 15.3	68.1 ± 18.5	76.8 ± 15.9	63.2 ± 19.8
80	95.2 ± 11.6	71.8 ± 16.0	80.8 ± 13.1	42.3 ± 31.9

TABLE II: Distributions of the performance metrics in terms of mean (\pm SD) using the testing dataset.

a patient-tailored tuning of the parameters or the use of different signals for the residual generator block such as the COB and the ROC. These promising results are related to patients treated with BBT; as future developments, the method will be extended to patients treated with HCL AP.

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